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Planning the Future of Research & Innovation in the European University Alliance UNITE!

18-month coordination & management report with quality assessment

Deliverable 1.2

Deliverable

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Abstract	<p>The UNITE.H2020 management structures and operational procedures are intended to provide a flexible coordination of the UNITE.H2020 project activities, a smooth and swift decision process, a prompt management of risks and unforeseen events, and an efficient use of resources with the overall aim of ensuring a proper quality of the project activities.</p> <p>This document gives an overview of the coordination and management structure and procedure with a focus on the project quality assessment</p>
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v1.0	30 June 2022			Management Team (POLITO)		Final version to be submitted to EC

Abbreviation list

CA – Consortium Agreement
 PC - Project Coordinator
 MO - Management Office
 GA - General Assembly
 PO – Project Officer
 KLO - Key Liaison Officer
 UGP - Unite! Governing Platform
 SF – Stakeholder Forum
 DMP - Data Management Plan
 WPL – Work Package Leader
 WPLB - Work Package Leaders’ Board
 GDPR - General Data Protection Regulation
 ORD - Open Research Data

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1 Introduction

The UNITE.H2020 management structures and operational procedures are intended to provide a flexible coordination of the UNITE.H2020 project activities, a smooth and swift decision process, a prompt management of risks and unforeseen events, and an efficient use of resources with the overall aim of ensuring a proper quality of the project activities.

This document (Deliverable 1.2 “18-month coordination & management report with quality assessment”) gives an overview of the coordination and management structure and procedures with a focus on the project quality assessment.

A summary of the the management structure and the role of each management bodies, which are clearly described also in the project Grant Agreement and in the Consortium Agreement (CA), are presented, as well as the management activities and procedures. Most of these activities are carried out to ensure a proper quality management as well as risk assessment. In fact, the quality level of all the project activities and the respect of the Gantt Chart are pursued through the constant internal monitoring activity and the regular update of the risk assessment as well as with effective communication with the partners to ensure a clear presentation of the management structure, internal procedures, processes and work methods and a constant update of the common understanding of the project objectives.

The quality assessment of the project activities in the first half of the project is discussed at the end of the document.

2 UNITE.H2020 Management Bodies and tasks

The project coordination and management structure, which is described in full detail in the Grant and Consortium Agreement, is summarized in Figure 1 and in the following Sections.

Figure 1 - UNITE.H2020 coordination and management structure

2.1 Project Coordinator and Management Office

The project Coordinator (PC) is in charge for operatively managing the project and is supported by the project **Management Office (MO)** (Research Support Office at POLITO) for day-to-day project communication and project management for the administrative and financial issues, approval of the deliverables and reports for EC and project data management. In collaboration with WPLB: PO/MO collect contributions from the consortium for the monitoring and reporting activity; ensure the quality level of all the activities; carry out milestone review and update of the risk analysis and assessment; propose corrective action to the General Assembly (GA). They are in charge of the communication with the Project Officer (PO).

2.2 Work Package Leaders (WPLs) and Work Package Leaders' Board (WPLB)

The Work Package Leaders (WPLs) supervises the WP activities and draft the WP deliverables, in collaboration with the **Task Leaders**.

The WP Leaders' Board (WPLB), the executive and technical body of the project composed by the WPLs, presents the project achievements to the General Assembly (GA) during the Plenary meetings; collect contributions from the consortium for the monitoring and reporting activity every six months; ensures the quality level of all the activities; carries out milestone review and update of the risk analysis and assessment; proposes corrective action to the General Assembly GA; meet every six months to collect information on the project progress and in extraordinary meetings to discuss specific topics.

2.3 General Assembly (GA)

The General Assembly (GA) is the decision-making body of the consortium. It was created at the beginning of the project. The GA is composed by 2 representatives per partner: each partner is represented by the Key Liaison Officer (KLO - Unite! Alliance representative, already appointed by each Unite! partner to coordinate the activities of the partner institution within the Unite! Alliance) and by another representative appointed by each partner. The GA is chaired by the UNITE.H2020 coordinator. The Unite! Secretary General also convene the GA as auditor in his role of operational manager of the Unite! E+ pilot project and of the Unite! Alliance. The GA is responsible for the yearly supervision of the project during the Plenary Meetings and gives direction of the project in terms of overall strategy and for the decision regarding any change in the action plan. The Unite! Secretary General will also convene the GA as auditor.

2.4 Unite! Governing Platform (UGP)

The Unite! Governing Platform (UGP), the Unite! Alliance internal Advisory Board participated by the Presidents and Rectors of all Unite! Universities, ensures, in collaboration with the GA, the coherence between the UNITE.H2020 and the Unite! Alliance goals.

2.5 UNITE.H2020 Stakeholders Forum (SF)

The process of creation of the Stakeholder Forum, an advisory board for UNITE.H2020, was initiated in February 2022 by contacting a group of stakeholders selected on the basis of the stakeholder list provided by WP2, WP4 and WP7, the current partners' collaborations with them and the available contacts. The SF members were invited to attend the UNITE.H2020 plenary meeting on 10th March 2022.

3 UNITE.H2020 management activities and procedures

The different project management activities are schematized in Figure 2. The activities and related procedures, described in the following Section, have been clearly presented to the WP leaders and the whole consortium during the WPLB and project plenary meetings.

Figure 2 – Schematic representation of the different management activities in UNITE.H2020

3.1 Administrative and financial issues

PC and MO, with the support of all the other partners, are in charge of administrative and financial issues. The Coordinator receive the payments from the Funding Authority and distribute it to the Partners, according to what stated in the Consortium Agreement.

3.2 Data management

PC and MO drafted the UNITE.H2020 Data Management Plan (DMP) – Deliverable 1.1 – which was revised by all the project partners. It was submitted in June 2021 (M6) and updated in June 2022 (M18). The DMP describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated during the project and after the project end, providing common guidelines as suggestion for the UNITE.H2020 consortium for the management of the project research data in accordance with the FAIR data principle, EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the Open Research Data (ORD) pilot requirements for open access provision to the results associated to the peer-reviewed publications.

Depending on the type and format of the research project data, different storage and sharing systems are used in UNITE.H2020 (see Figure 3):

- **Partner’s project data:** each partner stores its UNITE.H2020 data on the storage system at its own facilities.
- **WP’s data:** WP research data are stored on Microsoft Team (PRJ-UNITE_H2020 team) or on other systems on the basis of the WPL evaluation.
- **Project relevant data:** relevant data to be shared among the whole consortium / whole Unite! alliance are stored on uShare project repository (<https://ushare.unite-university.eu/#/>) or, for collaborative files, on Microsoft Team (PRJ-UNITE_H2020 team). The Data Management Plan was shared on uShare repository.

Figure 3 – Data type and storage/sharing systems in UNITE.H2020

In addition to the above-mentioned data storing and sharing systems, UNITE.H2020 will consider to use specific repositories (e.g. Zenodo) for the research data that the consortium will decide to make open. Moreover, the consortium will use the Metacampus, the Moodle platform already used by the Unite! alliance, to host the UNITE.H2020 initiatives and share data.

Other data storing and sharing systems, related to communication and dissemination activities, are the Unite! (<https://www.unite-university.eu/>) and the partner’s websites with pages dedicated to Unite! and associated projects, the Alliance social media (i.e. Twitter, YouTube channel, LinkedIn) and the partner’s OA publications institutional repositories.

The data management is carried out in accordance with the FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable) data principles.

The use of **metadata**, consisting in all the data-related information, contributes to make data FAIR. For the most relevant and official documents, such as the project deliverables/ reports/ white papers, a common template is used with the metadata to be included at the beginning of the document (e.g. Date, Author, Document title, Project Title, Reference WP etc.).

With the aim of making data **FINDABLE**, as a general rule, clear **naming and organization** of the project data in the different storing and sharing systems is carried out to favour data discoverability. A shared **naming convention** is also used for the data file, as reported below.

```
<date:yyyy.mm.dd>_UNITE.H2020_<WP
number>_<description1>_<description2>_<person(s)/partner(s)>_<file version>_rev <revising
partner>_<date of revision>_upd<dd.Month.yyyy>.<ext>
```

Date: date of the event to which it is referred, such as a meeting, workshop

Project name: UNITE.H2020

WP number: for data referred to a specific WP

Description1: Main topic/ event to which the file is referred

Description2 (3, 4..): further information to better describe the topic

Person(s)/Partner(s): SurnameN of author(s) or person(s)/partner(s) the file is referred to

File version: for file derived by a revision procedure (e.g. periodic revision of the Data Management Plan, revision procedure of a Deliverable by partners)

Partner(s)/person(s) revising the file

Date of revision

Date of update: for files subjected to periodic update

File extension

As regards **ACCESSIBILITY**, the consortium aims at maximising the access to the research data generated by the projects. In addition to publications and related research data, each WP leader can propose a set of data to be made **openly available** over the course of the project, which has to be approved by the whole consortium, in accordance with the Grant Agreement. Most of the data will be text documents, presentations, spreadsheets, images, audio and video, usually requiring **common software** to access the data, which will promote also data **INTEROPERABILITY**. For what concerns the data **RE-USABILITY**, each partner is responsible to ensure data quality during data collection, generation, data entry or digitalisation and data checking. Moreover, the licences needed to access the UNITE.H2020 data will be evaluated over the course of the project on a case-by-case evaluation (preferably CC-BY and CC0 licence).

Each beneficiary should ensure adequate **backup and data recovery system** for its own research data stored at their local storage systems. Data recover on uShare repository can be done through the ATIC service at UPCnet, which developed the uShare repository for the Unite! Alliance. Default backup policy establishes daily copies are done with a 28 days retention period (availability). Also,

aimed to guarantee system continuity in case of disaster, a full backup with 1 year retention period is made every trimester. Data recovery on Microsoft Team can be done through the SharePoint.

The partner collecting the **personal and sensitive data** will be responsible for their collection and management in accordance with the EU GDPR (further details in the Grant Agreement, CA and UNITE.H2020 DMP). Data containing sensitive personal data will be stored by the responsible partner together with the privacy consent forms in secure password protected environments according to the EU GDPR. Further details can be found in Section 6 Ethical aspects.

As required by the Grant Agreement, each beneficiary should ensure the **archiving and preservation** of the data for a period of five years after the payment and until the end of any on-going checks, reviews, audits, investigations, litigation or the pursuits of claims under the Agreement. The possibility and the modality of data storage for a longer time period will be discussed and evaluated among the partners (e.g. Zenodo repository for open data).

3.3 Communication for management

The MO and PC at POLITO are in charge of the communication with the project partners for the project coordination, management and partner support. They are daily engaged in email exchange and meetings for the coordination of the project activities and for the support of the partners for any specific requests. A frequent communication between **MO** and **PC** allows a constant update on the progress of the project and the discussion of any daily issues. An ad hoc email address has been created - **UNITE.H2020_management@polito.it** - for the project official email communication from and to the MO. Figure 4 shows the project management information flow.

Figure 4 - Project management information flow

The project management information flow can be summarized as follows:

- **MO/PC** communicate to the **whole consortium** to give general information and updates on the project activities
- **WPLs and PC/MO** have a direct communication for any relevant information/ issue regarding the project or the specific WP (e.g. to ask for/ respond to specific requests on WP activity implementation, for the WPLB meeting organization and for the project monitoring activity). When possible, the WPLs act as an intermediary for the communication between the PC/MO and the WP participants. However, when needed, also one-to-one communication and ad-hoc meetings are also organized with single project participants to discuss any possible problems/ deviations
- **WPLs** contact the partner **WP9 contact person** of his/her institution for the external dissemination of WP activities (PC/MO in copy)
- **MO/PC** contact the **Unite! Alliance Secretariat** for Unite! internal communication and dissemination, relevant for the Unite! Alliance as well as when a synergy with the Unite! alliance is needed.
- **PC/MO** act as intermediary for the communication between the UNITE.H2020 consortium and the **PO** for any relevant issue regarding the project (i.e. administrative, financial, reporting issues).

3.4 Project meetings

MO/PC are in charge for the organization, preparation and guidance the project meetings. They communicate with the meeting participants to agree on the date, define the Agenda with the PC and draft the presentation templates. After the meeting, the MO and PC draft the meeting Minutes, upload all the meeting-related documents (agenda, presentations, minutes) on the WP1 community in uShare project repository. The planned project meetings are reported in the following:

- **Plenary meetings**, involving the whole consortium (4 meetings, including Kick-off and Final meeting)
- **WPLB meetings**, involving WPLs and chaired by PC, organized every 6 months to report on the progress of the WP activities
- **GA meetings**, involving the GA members with the Unite! Secretary general as auditor.

Table 1 summarizes the project meetings in the first reporting period (January 2021 – June 2022)

Table 1 – UNITE.H2020 meetings in the first reporting period (M1-M18)

Plenary meetings (whole consortium) – annual meetings		
<i>Date</i>	<i>Place</i>	<i>Comments</i>
29 January 2021	online (due to COVID restrictions)	KOM- Originally planned in Torino
10 March 2022	online (due to COVID restrictions)	Originally planned in Stockholm in occasion of the 5 th Unite! Dialogue It was organized online due to COVID restrictions

WPLB meetings (WPLs) - every 6 months		
<i>Date</i>	<i>Place</i>	<i>Comments</i>
14 June 2021	online (as planned)	
1-2 December 2021	Barcelona (hybrid)	Originally planned to be online It was organized in Barcelona in occasion of the 4 th Unite! Dialogue in hybrid format
21 January 2022	(online)	Extraordinary meeting Discussion about the plan for the WP pilots for the R&I action plan
15 June 2022	Stockholm (hybrid)	Originally planned to be online It was organized in Stockholm in hybrid format in occasion of the Unite! summer community event
General Assembly meetings (GA members; Secretary General)		
<i>Date</i>	<i>Place</i>	<i>Comments</i>
10 March 2022	online (due to COVID restrictions)	Originally planned in Stockholm in occasion of the 5 th Unite! Dialogue It was organized online due to COVID restrictions

3.5 Quality management and risk assessment

The Project Coordinator (PC) and the Management Office (MO) aim at ensuring the proper quality management of the project and the respect of the Gantt Chart with their day-do-day activities, that can be summarized as follow:

- **Clear presentation to the partners of the project internal procedures.** The Project Coordinator (PC) and the Management Office (MO) aim at ensuring the proper quality management of the project through a clear communication and presentation to partners of the management structure and the internal procedures, processes and work methods. MO always aims at making clear communications in the documents, meeting or email exchange and it is at the partners' disposal for any needed clarifications about the internal procedures. PC and MO usually present the procedures to the whole partnership during the project meeting or by email (e.g. communication flow; overview of the data storage/ sharing systems; the internal deadlines and procedure for the deliverable revision and submission; the internal monitoring and reporting documents and procedure).
- **Constant update of the common understanding of the project objectives.** During the preparation of the proposal, all partners have contributed to a common understanding of the objectives and the content of the project. A constantly updating this common understanding is needed in order to ensure the positive project performance and the compliance with the objectives. This is carried out through the work presentation and discussion during the periodic meetings with WPLs (Work Package Leaders' meetings, every 6 months), as well with *ad hoc* organized meetings, when needed.

- **Internal monitoring activity (see Section 3.5.1).** PC, MO, WPLs and WPLB are responsible for ensuring the quality level of all the activities by constantly monitoring the project progress and the respect of the GANTT chart. The monitoring activity was carried out by the WPLs for their WP and by PC/MO for the whole project through: a regular communication among PC, MO and WPLs; the collection of information from WPLs every six months about the project progress and expected deviations with *ad-hoc* internal documents (i.e. Progress Report, Deviations' table, Communication & Dissemination Summary Table); WPLs presentations during the WPLB meeting every 6 months. On the basis of the collected information, MO and PC evaluate and discuss any possible issues/ deviations with WPLs and, for major changes affecting the project, with the General Assembly for its approval. Then, if necessary, MO and PC communicate/ discuss it with the PO evaluating the need for an official request of amendment.
- **Regular update of the risk assessment (see Section 3.5.2).** A regular update (at least annually) of the risk analysis and assessment is carried out to verify if the risk materialized, the application of the mitigation actions and to detect any unforeseen risk.

The monitoring activity and risk assessment allowed to check also the attainment of Milestones and Deliverables and to detect deviations/ problems to timely evaluate proper corrective measures and communicate with the Project Officer (if needed).

3.5.1 Internal monitoring activity

PC, MO, WPLs and WPLB are responsible for ensuring the quality level of all the activities by constantly monitoring the project progress and the respect of the GANTT chart.

Each WPLs monitor the activity of the WP (e.g. through coordination of the WP activities, communication with the WP team, organization of regular WP meetings etc.).

PC/MO, in collaboration with WPLs, are responsible for the internal monitoring of the whole project with a regular communication among PC, MO and WPLs and the collection of information from WPLs every six months on the project progress for to assess the compliance with the GA through the drafting of some periodic documents as well as with the reporting of the activity progress during the WPLB meetings every six months.

➤ Periodic documents on project progress.

MO prepared some documents for the internal monitoring of the project progress (i.e. Progress Report, Deviations' Table and C&D Summary Table) and planned their periodic update with the active involvement of all the partners. These documents are also the basis for the drafting of the Periodic Report that has to be submitted to the EC at the end of each UNITE.H2020 reporting periods (M18 and M36), as reported in Section 3.6.

MO prepared the following documents (shared on Microsoft Teams - PRJ-UNITE-H2020 team - for collaborative editing) for the internal monitoring activity related to the project progress and planned their periodic update with the active involvement of all the partners (Figure 5):

- **Progress Report:** collecting information about the project progress, including a technical report of the WP activities and the update of the risk analysis and assessment – drafted by WPLs with the supervision of PC/ MO every 6 months – it is used for the monitoring of the project progress. This will also be the basis for the drafting of the Periodic Report.
- **Deviations’ table:** collecting information about the project deviations - drafted by WPLs with the supervision of PC/ MO whenever a deviation is foreseen and before it occurs/ to be checked every 6 months - it is used for the monitoring of the project progress and as a basis for the drafting of the Periodic Report
- **Communication & Dissemination Summary Table:** collecting information about the WP9 activities – drafted by WP9 team with the supervision of WP9 leader/ PC/ MO over the course of the project and checked every 6 months – serves to WP9 to evaluate overall WP9 activity and the aggregated data are used for the continuous reporting activity

	Who	Supervision	When
Progress report	WPLs	PC and MO	Every 6 months
Deviations’ Table	WPLs	PC and MO	whenever a deviation is foreseen and before it occurs + Verification every 6 months
Communication and Dissemination Table	WP9	WP9 Leader / PC and MO	Over the course of the project + Verification every 6 months

Figure 5 Documents for the internal monitoring of the project progress

The documents, as well as their scope and planned periodic update, were shared with WPLs, WP9 and WP1 to get them involved in the monitoring and reporting activity. An email was sent to WPLs/ WP9 team with an explanation of the document scope in the context of the monitoring and reporting activity and the planned periodic request for their contribution, which were also detailed in the documents itself. The documents and the plan for their periodic update was also presented to WPLs in the first WPLB meeting (14 June 2021).

➤ **WPLB meetings**

The WPLB will convene every 6 months through remote meetings to ensure that the technical developments and general progress are well coordinated and in a timely way, or additional ad hoc meetings, upon WP leader request. WPLB meetings are the occasion to present the performed activities, to assess the proper advancement of the project and highlight any problems and expected deviations.

The monitoring activity of UNITE.H2020 can be summarized as follows:

Each WPL (all partners)

- supervise the activity of the WP

- report the WP activities every 6 months (Progress Report and WPLB meeting)
- communicate any deviation in time to PC and MO by email and by filing in the Deviations' Table whenever a deviation is foreseen and before it occurs

WP9 team (all partners)

- draft the Communication & Dissemination (C&D) Summary Table every 6 months with the supervision of the WP9 leader (UPC)

MO/ PC (POLITO)

- support the WPLs and WP9 team in their monitoring activity
- collect and analyze all the information of the Progress Report, Deviations' Table and the presentations of the WPLB meetings to monitor the progress of project activities and the potential deviations
- discuss with WPLs any issue/deviation to evaluate any possible corrective actions
- if any major changes affect the project, propose modifications of the action plan to the GA for its approval
- communicate with the Project Officer any relevant issue and deviation

3.5.2 Risk assessment and review

In the project proposal, a risk analysis has been performed to identify the potential critical issues that could hinder the full achievement of the project objectives, and ways to mitigate the possible effects of these critical issues were defined in order to minimize the potential shortcomings. This analysis has been updated by the WPLs and presented in occasion of the Milestones and Risk Analysis Review during the Plenary meeting on March 10th, 2022. A further update is being carried out at the moment to be included in the periodic report.

3.6 Reporting activity to EC

The PC/MO at POLITO are engaged in the reporting activities to EC with the support of all the consortium (especially WPLs and WP1 team). The information collected during the internal monitoring activity (see Section 3.5.1) are the basis for the reporting activity to EC. The reporting activities that have been carried out are the following:

- *Continuous reporting on the Funder&Tenders Portal:* over the course of the project, PC/MO updated the information on the Funding&Tenders portal related to the continuous reporting. One of the main activities is related to the submission of the Deliverables and reporting of the achieved Milestones (see Section 3.6.1 and Section 3.6.2). The data collected from the C&D summary Table are used for the reporting of the C&D activities on the EC portal.
- *Draft of the Periodic Report:* PC/MO supervised the drafting of the first periodic report related to the project progress in the first reporting period (M1-M18) with the collaboration of all the consortium, especially the WPLs and WP1 team. The documents resulting from the internal monitoring process (i.e. Progress Report, Deviations' table and C&D Summary Table) are used as a basis for the drafting of the Periodic Report. PC/MO collected all the contributions by WPLs, revised the document and, when needed, asked for WPLs' revision before submission to EC.

3.6.1 Drafting and timely submission of Deliverables

The internal procedure for the drafting and timely submission of Deliverables is shown in Figure 6.

The WPL, in collaboration with the WP team, draft the Deliverables and send it to PC/MO at least 15 days before the deadline for revision/ approval. After the revision, the final version of the Deliverable, approved by the PC, is submitted by the MO on the Funding&Tenders portal before the deadline. If a delay is expected, the WPL has to communicate and justify it with reasonable advance to the PC/MO, that will inform the PO to possibly agree on a new due date.

Figure 6 Procedure for timely submission of deliverables

3.6.2 Reporting of the achieved Milestones

The internal procedure for the reporting of the achieved Milestones is summarized in Figure 7. For each Milestone, the WPL inform the PC and MO as soon as a milestone is achieved together with the date of achievement. If the “means of verification” of the milestone indicated in the GA is a document/ report etc., the WPL send it to the MO (as internal documentation, not to be uploaded on the Funding&Tenders portal). If a delay is expected, the WPL has to communicate and justify it with reasonable advance to the PC and MO, that will inform the PO to possibly agree on a new due date.

Figure 7 Procedure for the reporting of the achieved Milestone

3.6.3 Periodic report and Review meeting

The information collected for the internal monitoring activity serves also as the basis for the drafting of the Periodic Report and the following review meeting.

The periodic reporting activity to EC can be summarized as follows:

Each WPL (all partners)

- give their contribution to the periodic reporting activity (M18, M36)

WP9 team (all partners)

- aggregate the data of the C&D Summary Table to obtain data for the continuous reporting

MO/PC

- supervise and coordinate the whole reporting activity asking the contribution to the WPLs
- collect/harmonize/revise the WPLs' contributions to the periodic
- submit the Periodic Report

4 Quality assessment in the first reporting period

4.1 Respect of deadlines for Deliverables' submission and Milestones' achievement

One of the main indicator of the quality of the UNITE.H2020 activities is the respect of the GANTT chart with the timely Deliverables' submission and Milestones' achievement. The internal procedures for Deliverable submission and communication of Milestone achievement were clearly presented to the WPLs and the whole consortium (see Section 3.6.1 and Section 3.6.2). The monitoring activity (i.e. progress report and Deviations' table) allowed the on-time individuation of any problems and the discussion about possible corrective actions. When a delay is foreseen for the submission of a Deliverable or the achievement of a Milestone, the PC and MO communicated it in advance to the Project Officer to justify the deviation and agree a new due date.

Table 2 summarizes the situation about the Deliverables' submission and Milestones' achievement in the first Reporting Period of UNITE.H2020 (M1-M18) with the indication of the delayed Deliverables and Milestones. As it possible to see in Table 2:

- Deliverables: all the 15 Deliverables of the first reporting period were submitted, with only 2 of them slightly delayed (1 month) with new due date agreed in advance with the Project Officer.
- Milestones: 9 Milestones were achieved by the due date. 1 Milestone (MS3) was achieved with 10 days of delay, with new due date agreed in advance with the Project Officer. The deadline of one Milestone (MS9) was incorrectly indicated in M12 and the correct due date (M33) was communicated and agreed with the Project Officer. MS1 - First periodic review – has due date at M18, indicating the end of the first reporting period to which the first periodic review is referred.

Table 2 – UNITE.H2020 submitted Deliverables and achieved Milestones in the first reporting period (M1-M18).

Deliverables			
<i>Title</i>	<i>Due Date</i>	<i>Date of submission</i>	<i>Comment</i>
D1.1. - Data Management Plan	30 Jun 2021	29 Jun 2021	
D9.1 - Communication plan	30 Jun 2021	29 Jun 2021	
D2.1 - UNITE!Challenges and Convergences Roadmap	31 Aug 2021	30 Sept 2021	New due date agreed with PO
D3.1 - Report on existing RIs and other relevant information	31 Dec 2021	21 Dec 2021	
D5.1 - Handbook on HRS4R strategies, best practices and common strategies	31 Dec 2021	23 Dec 2021	
D6.1 - UNITE! Open science and innovation strategic roadmap	31 Dec 2021	22 Dec 2021	

D9.2 - Stakeholder map for communication and dissemination purposes adapted	31 Dec 2021	28 Jan 2022	New due date agreed with PO
D4.1 - Report on Preparation phase	28 Feb 2022	28 Feb 2022	
D7.1 - Repository of activities, best practices and channels for the citizens outreach, targeted SDGs and mapping of societal organisation	28 Feb 2022	28 Feb 2022	
D8.1. - A comparative report of European University Alliances and their complementarity to UNITE!	28 Feb 2022	28 Feb 2022	
D1.2 - 18-month coordination & management report with quality assessment	30 Jun 2022	30 Jun 2022	
D2.2 – UNITE.2020 Agenda and action plan	30 Jun 2022	30 Jun 2022	
D2.3 - 1st short policy brief (linked to the first reporting period)	30 Jun 2022	29 Jun 2022	
D4.2 - Report on Minimum Viable Solution	30 Jun 2022	30 Jun 2022	
D9.3 – Dissemination plan	30 Jun 2022	27 Jun 2022	
Milestones			
<i>Title</i>	<i>Due Date</i>	<i>Date of achievement</i>	<i>Comment</i>
MS7 - UNITE! HRS4R workshop	31 Mar 2021	26 Mar 2021	
MS18 - Communication plan agreed by all partners ready	30 Jun 2021	29 Jun 2021	
MS11 - Stakeholders identified and consolidated	31 July 2021	16 July 2021	
MS5 - Measuring the application of the lean approach with a pilot	30 Sept 2021	30 Sept 2021	
MS12 - UNITE! Researchers night	30 Nov 2021	24 Sept 2021	
MS4 - Thematic Collaborating Groups	31 Dec 2021	30 Nov 2021	
MS8 - Design a common framework to enable Talent Promotion	31 Dec 2021	21 Dec 2021	
MS14 - Selection of other European University Alliances for collaboration agreed	31 Dec 2021	07 Sept 2021	
MS9 - Paving the way for the future workshop	31 Dec 2021		Error in the WP description. Correct due date (October 2023) agreed with the PO
MS3 - Approval of the initial R&I	28 Feb 2022	10 Mar 2022	New due date agreed with PO
MS1 - First periodic review	30 June 2022		The date is referred to the end of the first reporting period
Dissemination plan	30 Jun 2022	27 Jun 2022	

4.2 Results of the monitoring activity, risk assessment and deviations' management

The MO and PC monitoring activity was carried out with the collection of WPLs information about the project activities progress through:

- *Sharing ad-hoc created documents for the internal monitoring process every 6 months (i.e. Progress Report, Deviations' table and C&D Summary Table):* the documents were shared at M6 and at M12. At the end of the first reporting period (M18) these documents were used as a basis for the drafting of the Periodic Report.
- *WPLs' presentation during the WPLB meetings* organized every 6 months and when it is needed: in the first reporting period (M1-M18) the WPLB meetings were organized in M6; M12; M13 (extraordinary meeting); M18

The procedures and documents used in UNITE.H2020 for the internal monitoring activity have been revised and improved over the course of the project also on the basis of the experience and WPLs' feedback. For example, the template for the progress report has been shortened to simplify the WPLs' drafting.

The contributions collect from WPLs through the documents and periodic WPLB meetings allowed the partners to be updated on the overall progress of the project. Moreover, on the basis of this information, the PC and MO verified the correct implementation of the project activities and, if needed, they asked the WPLs for clarification.

When a deviation was identified, the PC and MO discussed it with the WPLs to evaluate any possible corrective actions. In case of relevant issues/deviations (e.g. delay in the Deliverable submission or Milestone achievement; major deviations from the project plan), the PC and MO contacted in advance the Project Officer to justify it and agree the solution/new due date.

4.3 Results of the risk assessment and review

The WPLs performed a risk assessment and review in March 2022. They updated the risk analysis already included in the project. The analysis, that was presented in occasion of the Milestones and Risk Analysis Review during the Plenary meeting on 10 March 2022 included:

- the indication of the state of play of every foreseen risk (i.e. materialization of the risk, application of the risk mitigation measure): it was reported that some of the risk materialized (Risk 1-2-3-4). They were risks related to the delay in delivering the work (e.g. in relation to Deliverables and Milestones – Risk 2- maximum 1 month of delay for Deliverables and Milestones) or incorrect due date due to an error in the work package description (Risk 1; e.g. as in the case of MS9); Imperfect alignment with Unite! E+ (e.g. need for a clarification about the different scope and activities of the UNITE.H2020 and Unite! E+ project – Risk 3); Issues related to national specificities, diversified legislation and legal framework (Risk 4; e.g. for HR)

- the report of any unforeseen risk faced in the project/proposed risk mitigation measures: two unforeseen risks have been reported: Risk U1) Pandemic situation limiting face-to-face project meetings and events; the proposed mitigation measure is the organization of the project meetings and events online or in hybrid format when it does not affect the planned objectives, the expected impacts, and the results of the project.; Risk U2) Need to substitute the communication officer of the WPL partner; the proposed mitigation measure is the compensation by extra dedication of other team members during the transition period.

A further update is now ongoing to be included in the first periodic report. An update will be carried out at least annually over the course of the project.

